

Big Data to Enable Global Disruption of the Grapevine-powered Industries

D5.2 - Uncertainty-aware Visual Analytic Components

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ACRONYMS LIST

WP	Work package
MCMC	Markov chain Monte Carlo
ALFIS	Alcohol Fermentation Information System
HOP	Hypothetical Outcome Plots
SIS	Sequential Indicator Simulation

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this deliverable (D5.2), we demonstrate uncertainty-aware visual analytic components that highlight uncertainties in prediction outcomes. Previous research has shown the importance of showing uncertainty as they could improve awareness and trust of the readers, particularly non-expert users. With a growing awareness of the uncertainty problem, researchers have proposed to extend traditional visualisation techniques to represent the uncertainty information associated with data. Nonetheless, the application of uncertainty visualisations is limited in the agriculture domain.

To demonstrate our components, we initially used a stock price dataset obtained from Quandl. Later, as data from pilot partners became available, we integrated the data and redesigned the components. The dataset we used in this particular deliverable came from one of our pilot partners: INRA. The dataset contains alcoholic fermentation kinetics measured over time. The main attributes present in the dataset are the level of carbon dioxide (CO₂), temperature and time at measure. In this document, we present our uncertainty-aware visual analytic components and the development framework used to implement the components.

As the components are updated in the future versions, we will keep this document up to date accordingly. To keep track of such changes, please use this link: <http://bit.ly/2L7yMbp>.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Visualisation is considered as a powerful medium to help explore large datasets and to present meanings emerging from data. However, it is often impossible to encapsulate everything from real life in a dataset and to assume that the data being visualised are exact. When a data point illustrated in a graph, we tend to interpret it as a precise representation of the true data value (Wilke, 2019). It is difficult to assume that a data point could actually lie somewhere it has not been drawn. Nevertheless, this scenario is abundant in data visualisation. Nearly every data set has some uncertainty, and whether and how we choose to represent this uncertainty can make a major difference in how accurately one perceives the meaning of the data. Visualisation mechanisms for communicating uncertainty have proven to be successful gaining trust particularly for non-expert users (Kay et al., 2016). Besides, the incorporation of uncertainty into the decision-making process is crucial for making decisions and maximising benefits (Daradkeh and Abul-Huda, 2017).

There is a growing awareness of the uncertainty problem within the visualisation community. Thus, researchers have been extending many traditional techniques to represent not just the data, but also the uncertainty information associated with the data (Brodlić et al., 2012). Two commonly used approaches to indicate uncertainty are error bars and confidence bands (Wilke, 2019) (see Figure 1 for example). As we can see in the figure, the two approaches are derived from the classic box-and-whisker plot. The two approaches have been widely used to indicate uncertainty because they are precise, space efficient and can show the uncertainties of many different parameter estimates in a single graph. A data point on the line may represent a mean or median whereas a bar or band may show coverage (e.g. confidence intervals or standard error).

Figure 1. Example charts showing a confidence band (left) and error bars (right)¹

Nowadays, understanding uncertainty especially in prediction tasks is perhaps one of the greatest scientific challenges (Brodlić et al., 2012). It impacts on many crucial issues facing the world today—from climate studies (Potter et al., 2009), (Pöthkow et al., 2011) to meteorology (Boller et al., 2010), (Sanyal et al., 2010) to interpretation of medical data (Schultz et al., 2013), (Ristovski et al., 2014), (Jiao et al., 2012). By conveying the possibility that a point estimate may vary, uncertainty visualisations allow users to make more informed decisions based on prediction models (Hullman et al., 2019). One example scenario that makes use of uncertainty visualisations may be the prediction of hurricane paths. Figure 2 shows contrasting hurricane trackers from 2011 made by New York Times² (left) and Stamen³ (right), both indicating the predicted path and strength of hurricane Irene. Here, the uncertainty visualisation was extremely crucial in planning evacuations based on the predicted hurricane path.

¹ <https://alesandrab.wordpress.com/2014/09/17/create-line-charts-with-confidence-bands/>

² <http://www.nytimes.com/projects/hurricanes/index.html#!/2011/Irene>

³ <https://stamen.com/>

Figure 2. Hurricane trackers from 2011 made by New York Times (left) & Stamen (right) used to track the uncertainty over the strength and direction of Hurricane Irene

Another example would be the visualisation of future economic growth in the U.K. by the Bank of England (Spiegelhalter et al., 2011) as illustrated in Figure 3. The figure shows projections from November 2007 onward for changes in gross domestic product, with different shades indicating probability intervals. The black line indicates actual economic growth (according to the Office for National Statistics assessments) up to November 2007. The central interval (i.e. darker green) represents 10% probability, and the largest interval 90% probability.

Figure 3. Fan chart for future economic growth in the U.K. as recorded in November 2007 by the Bank of England

To demonstrate potential usefulness of uncertainty visualisations, we previously presented a number of visual analytic components using a stock price data obtained from Quandl⁴. These components are illustrated in Figure 4 which shows a combination of historical stock price and a projection for the next 12 months where the uncertainty visualisation is prominent. As data from the pilot partners became available, we decided to remodel the components to be able to integrate with the newly available data (see Section 2 for details).

⁴ <https://www.quandl.com/tools/api>

Figure 4. Uncertainty visualisation with stock price data

In the agriculture domain, the application of uncertainty visualisations is limited. CropGIS (Machwitz et al., 2018) uses a time-series to show information about biomass development of maize with a range of uncertainty describing various meteorological scenarios (see Figure 5). Weather is perhaps one of the most unpredictable variables that greatly affects agriculture. The uncertainty representations, therefore, better reflect the reality compared to static forecasts, making the prediction more reliable for farmers. Juang et al. (Juang et al., 2004) investigated the use of sequential indicator simulation (SIS) to model the uncertainty of mapping heavy-metal concentrations in soil. The result, for example, can be used to measure the reliability of delineating the contaminated area. This information is critical for decision-makers to determine which areas are contaminated and require cleanup actions.

Figure 5. CropGIS showing biomass development of maize with a range of uncertainty

Despite the importance of illustrating uncertainty in visualisations, the agriculture domain has not seen many applications of uncertainty. Moreover, in winemaking the kinetics and duration of fermentations could vary

significantly as a function of must composition and thermal conditions (Goelzer et al., 2009). This makes it difficult to manage fermentation tanks and power use in wine production. Visual-assisted prediction tools have been shown useful (Wachowiak et al., 2017) in precision agriculture but could mislead the end-users if uncertainty information is left out (Kay et al., 2016). Therefore, in this deliverable (D5.2), we aim to propose uncertainty-aware visual analytic components to assist with decision making of the pilot partners.

This document is structured as follows. Chapter 1 lays out an introduction to the deliverable describing the existing work and motivations. In Chapter 2, the visualisation components together with their development framework are described in detail. This document concludes with Chapter 3 where a summary of the deliverable is underlined.

In this version of D5.2, we focus on the alcoholic fermentation kinetic dataset provided by one of the pilot partners: INRA. Future versions will focus on integrating different data from more pilot partners. In the next section, we describe the system components, including the dataset, visualisations, and development framework we employed.

2 SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

2.1 DATASET

As a starting point for this version of the deliverable, we used an alcoholic fermentation kinetic dataset obtained from one of the pilot partners: INRA. The dataset contains a series of measurements made during the fermentation process of wine. These measurements include: accumulated CO₂ (mL), debit CO₂ (g), assigned temperature (degree C), elapsed time (hr) and timestamp (dd/mm/yyyy mm:hh). Figure 6 shows one of the current visualisation components being used by INRA, which is part of the Alcohol Fermentation Information System (ALFIS) and allows experts to compare the CO₂ levels over time across previous fermentation experiments. Prediction of any sort is not currently supported by the ALFIS system.

Since fermentation is assumed to be completed once the CO₂ level hits zero, we developed a model to predict the time at which the CO₂ level might reach zero. Prediction outputs are then visualised integrating uncertainty in the outputs. To demonstrate this, from a large set of fermentation experiments conducted by INRA, we selected data from the experiments that are focused on the Carignan variety as they had abundant measurements. Because the temperature was kept constant during these experiments, we did not include the temperature in the predictions. In the following subsections, we describe the dataset, components and development framework.

Figure 6. A visualisation component of the alcohol fermentation information system currently being used by INRA

2.2 VISUALISATION COMPONENTS

Multiple visualisations have been designed to show the prediction of the debit CO₂ level of a fermentation. The developed prediction model allows us to incorporate uncertainty into the visualisation which further supports to address the following questions:

- Is there an anomaly on the fermentation process? i.e. is the behaviour of the current fermentation proceeding as expected and is it indeed similar to the reference experiments?
- When can we expect the fermentation to end? i.e. when will the fermentation process stop producing CO₂?

In addition, we believe that comparing the outcome of the current fermentation with the ones projected by the model can help detect anomalies. Figure 7 highlights such a case where anomalies, depicted in the yellow/black lines, can be seen in comparison to the outcomes projected by the model, depicted in the blue uncertainty bands.

Figure 7. An example output highlighting anomalies in the current experiment (yellow/black lines) compared to the outcomes predicted by the model (blue uncertainty bands)

2.2.1 Prediction Model

As mentioned in Section 2.1, our predictions are based on similar previous fermentation experiments. They can be selected by the similarity on any feature of the fermentation process (e.g. origin of the must, temperature, fermentation characteristics) or by the similarity of the start of the fermentation process. In the following example, the similarities have been selected based on the latter: similarity of the start of the fermentation process.

Figure 8. The experiments we are interested in and the selected experiments based on the first 71:43 hours. 10% experiments with the lower mean absolute error were selected

A Bayesian statistical inference with Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling model (using B-splines⁵) has been developed in Stan⁶, a state-of-the-art platform for statistical modelling. The model description can be found in the file `src/models/fermentation.stan` within the project folder⁷ (see Section 2.3 to obtain the project).

Next, various different versions of the uncertainty visualisations are described. The visualisations have been developed with `tidybayes` (Kay, 2018) and `ggplot2` (Wickham, 2016) libraries.

2.2.2 Spaghetti Visualisation

For this visualisation N samples are drawn from the model, that we visualised together with a current experiment. N should be high enough to show enough variation of the possible outcomes. In the following figure we see an example of this visualisations with 100 samples drawn from the model.

Figure 9. Spaghetti visualisation showing 100 samples from our model. In dark grey the current experiment values are drawn, and in light grey/blue, the samples evolution before/after the running time

⁵ https://mc-stan.org/users/documentation/case-studies/splines_in_stan.html

⁶ <https://mc-stan.org/>

⁷ <https://github.com/BigDataGrapes-EU/deliverable5.2>

The following figure shows how the current fermentation ended compared to the samples:

Figure 10. Spaghetti visualisation (Figure 9) with the evolution of the current fermentation process in orange

2.2.3 Uncertainty Bands Visualisation

For this visualisation different percentage prediction intervals of debitCO₂ as a function of the Elapsed Time are drawn. Each interval represents the region within which the model expects to find X % of the actual debit CO₂ levels in the model population (all the past and future possible fermentation processes modelled by our similarity criteria), at each moment in time.

Figure 11. Uncertainty bands visualisation showing the 50%, 80% and 95% prediction intervals of debitCO₂ as a function of the Elapsed Time. The dark grey line shows the current experiment. The light grey/blue areas show the intervals before/after the running time

The following figure shows how the current fermentation ended compared to the samples:

Figure 12. Uncertainty bands visualisation (Figure 11) with the evolution of the current fermentation process in orange

2.2.4 Gradient Visualisation

If a high increment on the number of intervals takes place, we obtain what is known as a Gradient Visualisation, where the opacity signals how much the model expects to find the actual debit CO₂ levels in the model population at each moment in time. It can be seen on the following figure:

Figure 13. Gradient visualisation. The dark grey line shows the current experiment values. The light grey/blue areas show the gradient before/after the running time

The following figure shows how the current fermentation ended compared to the samples:

Figure 14. Gradient visualisation (Figure 13) with the evolution of the current fermentation process in orange

2.2.5 Hypothetical Outcome Plots (HOPs) Visualisation

Similarly to the spaghetti visualisation, hypothetical outcome plots (HOPs) (Kale et al., 2019), (Hullman et al., 2015) use samples and not prediction intervals. But, instead of all the samples at a time, it shows one sample at a time in an animation.

Figure 15. HOP visualisation. Four of the 100 frames with a different sample in each.

Another option is to add a static low opacity version of all samples in the background. In Figure 16, we can see one example frame of this version.

Figure 16. HOP visualisation with static background using 100 samples

2.3 DEVELOPMENT FRAMEWORK

All the development has been carried out using the R language⁸. The codes have been published at the github repository of BigDataGrapes (<https://github.com/BigDataGrapes-EU/deliverables.2>).

2.3.1 Data Munging

The sample data obtained from ALFIS system is located in the `data/raw/Carignan_k1.csv` file within the project. Given an experiment (EXPERIMENT column) and an elapsed time (RUNNING_TIME column) the mock data for a prediction scenario can be generated from the file `munge.R` which creates the following csv files:

- `data/interim/past_experiments.csv` This csv contains all the data from all experiments, except the selected one.
- `data/interim/running_experiment.csv` This csv contains the data from the selected (current) experiment until the elapsed time.
- `data/interim/experiment_future.csv` This csv contains the data from the selected (current) experiment after the elapsed time. This data can be used to simulate the final results of the fermentation process.

2.3.2 Analysis and Visualisation

All the necessary code to replicate the analysis and the different visualisations can be found in the file `src/fermentation.Rmd`. The Stan code for the model can be found in the file `src/models/fermentation.stan`.

A copy of the analysis report has been also generated on markdown format in the file `src/fermentation.md`.

⁸ <https://www.r-project.org/>

3 CONCLUSIONS

In this document, we presented our first version of an uncertainty-aware visual analytic components, delivered under the work package 5. Building upon the existing visual analytic components designed using a stock price dataset, we remodelled a number of new components. The aim was to be able to integrate with the newly available data from one of the pilot partners: INRA. In this version of the deliverable, we described these visualisations together with a development framework used to implement the visualisations.

We built the components using the R language with the help of a few open source visualisation libraries. Detailed explanations of the components and development framework have been presented in Chapter 2. We also provided sample codes for the components highlighting their reusability. All of the codes have been published at the github repository of BigDataGrapes (<https://github.com/BigDataGrapes-EU/deliverable5.2>).

For the next version of this deliverable, we will focus on integrating with different datasets from more pilot partners. In the meantime, we will also conduct evaluations of these visualisation components with pilot partners and expert users. It is hoped that the evaluations will be commenced by early May.

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